

DEVELOPMENT OF FUNCTIONAL LITERACY IN ENGLISH LESSONS

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The article considers the features of the development of functional literacy in English lessons. At present, laying the foundations of functional literacy, which helps the individual to function in society, is of considerable importance. The author of the article gives an analysis of practical techniques used in English lessons for the effective formation of reading literacy. The concept of learning research is given and its main components are explained. Recommendations are given for teachers to create a supportive school environment to motivate and engage students in active learning and research activities. Individualized approaches to learning and research allow for learning based on experience or discovery and contribute to the development of independence, reading literacy, creative thinking, global competence (idea development, assessment).

The article also presents the results of experiential learning, showing the effectiveness of the organization of educational and research activities for the development of functional literacy.

Keywords: functional literacy of students, formation of functional literacy, areas of functional literacy, English lesson, assignments.

Functional literacy is a method of orienting a person in society, which connects the educational and social activity of a person. It helps him to solve various problems related to human life on the basis of knowledge acquired in the process of education. The formation of this type of literacy makes it easier for an individual to understand issues of socialization, culture, politics and economics. The high level of functional literacy of mankind determines its social and cultural achievements. If the level remains low, this may affect the development of a social crisis. [1;206-208]

Functional literacy, according to A.A. Leontiev - the ability of a person to use the knowledge acquired during life to solve a wide range of life tasks in various areas of human activity, communication and social relations. [2;5-8]

Conscious education gives students the knowledge and access to the cognitive processes they need to effectively solve problems. [3]

However, it is well known that when working with texts, students in practice encounter many problems and difficulties, such as not knowing the meanings of many words, not being able to read diagrams, not being able to title texts, not understanding the meaning of what is written, not being able to highlight key words, not being able to formulate questions, not being able to choose solutions, not being able to implement existing skills, not being able to transfer knowledge and skills from one area to another and often being replaced by more familiar ones. All this is associated with insufficiently developed functional literacy. Functional literacy is "the ability to use reading and writing skills in social interactions (for example, when opening a bank account, reading instructions, filling out feedback forms), that is, the level of literacy at which a person enters into a relationship with the external environment

and is able to adapt and function in it as quickly as possible." [4;9-10]

It is important that teachers organize the learning process so that students can learn on their own. Teachers need to organize the learning process in such a way that students develop an independent way of learning - obtaining the necessary information, analyzing it and using it to solve problems in their lives. This can be achieved through classroom research, especially in English classes. Conducting educational research allows students to form and develop the ability to work with information, evaluate their own activities and represent. The results of this work are presented. Conducting academic research in the English classroom helps students develop functional literacy, that is, the skills to communicate freely and practically apply their knowledge in interaction with society. The main task of the teacher is to stimulate the speech-cognitive activity of students and create situational learning, in other words, to simulate learning situations that cause students to spontaneously speak. The main features of such situations are practical tasks, such as buying a movie ticket, ordering in a cafe or restaurant, deciding where to go, etc.

It is possible to use active literacy in the process of learning British English in different ways: games, songs, linguistic and cultural films and cartoons, listening exercises, speaking (development of monologue and dialogic speech), message, reading. The introduction of gambling technologies in the classroom not only solves the problem of student motivation, but is also considered an effective tool at the turn of strengthening knowledge of vocabulary and grammar. Which can be used for the intentional conclusion of inventive problems. A necessary component of the British lesson is the independent work of the student with the word. And

this should not be elementary reading and translation, but the performance of tasks for active literacy, that is, the compilation of the formation of active reading abilities. Without reading, mental formation and self-education is impossible, which lasts in the direction of all life. Use of active reading literacy with the development of lexical and grammatical abilities.

Problems can be: misunderstanding the meaning of the expression

- Highlighting the key thought in the text, the main tirades and main texts.
- Complete the table of contents with the content of the word with your own information (one / two or three words).

Problems can be: the lack of comprehensiveness of vocabulary

- Formation of questions to words with the support of supports: correlation of parts A and B
- Look for the misses in the proper questions.

Problems can be: incorrect interpretation of the content of the text; non-observance of the order of points of intent, illogical expression

- Fill in the table with the main texts that will be required to describe the part..
- Compose a data cluster h-l.
- Arrange the tirades from the monologue describing the drawings in the appropriate order.
- Mark those clichés that are necessary to describe the photo.
- What is not described in the text, mark with a "tick" / What questions can you answer?
- Edit the word (find language errors).

Problems can be inability to pronounce one's opinion on the word as a whole.

- Write down 3-4 (the most significant, in your opinion) phrases.
- Write down information that you would imagine... unusual / fascinating / necessary.

Problems can be inability to distinguish joint and distinctive properties.

- Prepare a list of important words/phrases to describe something.
- Underline in the text the opinions that characterize something.
- Arrange the following tirades in such a way that a logical, complete monologue expression directed to a specific topic comes out.
- Complete the table, focusing on the table of contents of the word.

The use of functional literacy in the lessons of the British language contributes to the successful learning of adolescents, accustoms them to work thoughtfully and actively with any text, which is actually quite important for the formation of communicative areas of responsibility. Using active literacy follows in the footsteps skillfully and competently, combining all kinds of educational pedagogical technologies in his own work.

The main Russian specialist in psychology and linguist, Aleksey Alekseevich Leontiev, wrote "A functionally intelligent person is a person who is able to apply all the knowledge, skills and abilities acquired every day in the direction of life to conclude a very

wide range of relevant tasks in various areas of human work, communication and public relations". [5;35]

A student who has developed the ability to actively read has the opportunity to "freely apply the ability to read and send messages to obtain information from the word - to understand it, compress it, rearrange it, etc." (A.A. Leontiev).

It is important to follow some rules for selecting continuous texts for tasks for functional reading:

The text should be interesting to the student.

The text should contain information unknown to the student.

The text should develop horizons.

The text should not be overloaded with numbers, dates, terms.

The illustrations are not distracting, but help to understand the content of the text. Illustrations should contribute to the development of cognitive activity.

The level of difficulty of the text should correspond to the age of the student. If necessary, adjust the text.

Unfamiliar words should be read by the teacher or presented in footnotes.

The volume of the text should not exceed the norm.

The text must be structured.

There should be no errors in the text. [6]

All of the above also applies to the word, which in terminology is not called a continuous word. These can be theater tickets, programs, posters, small posters, entrance tickets to cultural events, travel tickets, directions, exhibition and museum intentions, website screenshots, etc.

Thus, we see that the leading exercises for the formation of active literacy are considered to be all kinds of forms of work with the word-text.

As you know, in the educational literature, apart from reading and translation tasks, there are still pre-textual, textual and generalizing assignments. I did not want to belittle the role of listening to the word. Actually, this is listening - the process of perception and awareness of oral speech. This has the option of being a word that is read aloud, or a conversation of several people. Depending on the type of listening, after listening, the adept must briefly retell the leading meaning of what was said or answer questions about what he heard. Similar assignments are focused on one of the best understanding of the content of the word, on working out and assimilation of lexical and grammatical material, on the formation of the abilities of the message and oral speech, and also on the formation of all kinds of mental abilities, the ability to use information, analyze it, evaluate it.

In our own teaching practice, we often encounter countless shortcomings, tasks and difficulties that students have when working with a foreign word, but just:

- students do not understand the meaning of many texts, do not know the meaning of what is written or mark the main texts,

- cannot recite, read diagrams and title the word,

- unable to construct a question,

- do not have every chance to choose the method of concluding the problem,

– cannot update existing skills and/or move knowledge and skills from one area to another, etc.

The destruction of the tasks listed above and the formation of active literacy of students are facilitated by assignments with the introduction of words. In the original school, solid words are most often used, and it is important to observe some criteria for selecting these words with instructions for compiling active reading.

When preparing text material for work in a lesson, the teacher has the opportunity to autonomously create similar assignments, taking into account the course of the pedagogical process in the group, and also taking into account the individualities of students. With this assignment, they have every chance to be presented to students in a differentiated way, depending on their significance of mastering the language material. Work with the word has the opportunity to be realized both at the initial, for example, and at further stages of study.

For more advanced students, it is purposeful to develop and use assignments of increased difficulty, as well as problem assignments, to use words with a mental task.

Let's look at some of the types of tasks when working with a word.

Prior to text assignments, tasks are focused on modeling background knowledge that is important and necessary for the perception of a certain word, on eliminating the semantic and linguistic problems of its awareness and at the same time on compiling reading abilities and skills, developing an "understanding strategy", and forecasting skills. For example:

- read the title and say what (whom) will be discussed in the provided text;
- look at the photo; tell me what kind of life the people depicted in the photo have every chance to produce;
- describe the illustration (corresponding to the topic of the text); then read the word and find the misses in the picture;
- define the words to come;
- connect texts with their definitions;
- determine all possible meanings of the 1st total of the same word;
- find sentences with a specific grammatical form in the text;
- read the first sentences of the paragraphs and name the questions that will be considered in the text.

Subsequently, text instructions are provided to test reading comprehension, to control the degree of formed reading skills and the use of acquired information:

- answer questions about the content of the text;
- choose the correct answer (text content test);
- fill in the table according to the content of the text;
- number the actions in the order of their priority;
- fill in the sentences with texts from the text;
- express your opinion on what you have read;
- make questions to the text;
- prepare a retelling (annotation, review) of the word.

The task of forming active literacy in the lessons of the British language is to improve foreign language

areas of responsibility, the ability and readiness of adolescents to use the language to conclude communicative tasks. The main task of studying foreign languages is the formation of students of all types of speech work: reading, messages, dialogic and monologue speech Table of contents of the formation of active literacy in British language lessons:

- mastery of sensible oral and written speech;
- capacity for dialogue in a normal current situation;
- ability to express problem independently

The study of a foreign language contributes to the development of a person who is able to solve linguistic problems. The development of linguistic and communicative competence is associated with the development of functional literacy, which is understood as mastery of literate written and oral speech, the ability to interact in various life situations, the ability to express one's opinion on various problems, the ability to independently formulate problems and propose solutions to them.

The study of English is an important aspect of the formation of functional literacy. It allows you to develop literate speech and social skills, as well as to train specialists in various fields. [7;336]

Continuity is also important for the development of functional literacy in teaching English in educational institutions. How is continuity in teaching foreign languages ensured? The keys to continuity are a smooth transition from one level of education to another, a smooth complication of tasks, repetition and consolidation of the material covered. The task is facilitated if the teaching methods are harmonized and structured in a step-by-step system. Foreign language teachers must be literate and know the entire course of study, and not just the first-year program. [8;116]

Students who have developed functional reading and writing skills can use different kinds of reading systems (introductory, introductory, and reading comprehension). They are able to move from one reading and comprehension system to another suitable for one purpose of reading and comprehension or type of text. [4]

In the work of A.A. Leontiev gives a definition of functional literacy. If formal literacy is the acquisition of skills in the technique of reading, then functional literacy is the availability of these skills at the disposal of a person to extract information from a real text - its understanding, compression and transformation. [9;13-17]

Consequently, when organizing the educational process, teachers create conditions conducive to the formation (and later development) of the functional literacy of students:

1. Strengthen the interaction between teachers in order to exchange experience.
2. Select tasks with too much or too little information (which contributes to the formation of a critical attitude towards various types of texts) and "go beyond" tasks.
3. Use a variety of sources of information (both traditional textbooks, workbooks, educational films, and modern ones - the Internet, news channels, thematic videos, social networks).

4. Pay more attention to the formation of interdisciplinary knowledge and skills (for example, the formulation of a hypothesis, goal setting, generalization, analysis, synthesis, systematization and forecasting). [9;13-17]

When selecting texts, the following criteria are used: relevance of the text for students; taking into account the age characteristics of the target group (text adaptation); the presence of new information (for students); the presence of facts, concepts, names, places, products, numbers, dates, etc.; the presence of illustrations, diagrams and drawings; the presence of "factual opinions" in the text. Functional reading comprehension tests are characterized by "a large amount of text", "non-adaptive text", "information presented in the form of pictures, diagrams, tables of graphs", "tasks that require the integration of knowledge from different subjects" and "tasks in which it is not clear which area of knowledge should be addressed".

When choosing a sequence of texts for a task on functional reading, it is important to follow several rules:

1. The text should be of interest to students.
2. It must contain information that is unknown to the student.
3. The text should broaden the student's horizons.
4. Do not use too many numbers, dates or terms.
5. Illustrations should be unobtrusive and help students understand the content of the text.
6. The level of complexity of the text should correspond to the age of the children. Texts should be arranged as needed.
7. Unfamiliar words should be "read out" from the text or presented in footnotes.
8. Text length must not exceed the standard length
9. The font should make it easier for students to read the text.
10. Text should be structured.
11. There should be no errors in the text.

Reading literacy is based on the ability to understand and use texts. By developing this skill, students develop the ability to think and read, which in turn allows them to read and speak a foreign language fluently.

By developing these literacy skills, students will be able to:

-develop the ability to easily extract the necessary information from the text, understand the content of the text, form the main ideas and theses.

-develop the skills of processing and analyzing texts, comparing information of different nature and identifying specific problems in texts with existing theses.

-develop the skills of using information from texts to solve practical problems.

The development of creative thinking, which is at the heart of functional literacy, is the ability to productively evaluate and improve the ways in which new knowledge is acquired. Creative thinking is the ability to meaningfully apply acquired knowledge in real life.

An example of the use of creative reading and writing literacy in the English classroom is the role-

playing technique. Language games are understood as games that develop skills based on various language symbols (from syllables to houses of text). Such games include building words and sentences, drawing up monologues and dialogues. Language games are exercises that are carried out in pairs or groups at certain stages to consolidate and activate language material and teach simple and complex speech. They are characterized by static, prompts, imitative and reproductive activities, explicit or limited answers and competition.

The role-playing game is used when presenting new material, consolidating skills, summarizing and reviewing, as well as when students work independently. The role-play can be based on dialogue and text in a supervised way. Students become familiar with the dialogue material, choose and practice it. With the help of the teacher, they discuss the meaning and vocabulary of the dialogue and offer their own speech patterns. This allows students to develop their language and communication skills and build interesting learning processes. The final result of the work is evaluated by the teacher, who can also ask specific questions corresponding to the genre of dialogue.

Some exercises are used to teach reading literacy and creative thinking skills. Allows students to develop their hearing. May include interrogative exercises with various melodic shades, using many dots and cues of varying complexity. This is a variation of medium complexity. Students can simplify their version of the dialogue by entering phrases that they understand. Knowledge control is carried out in the form of translation and retelling in their native language. Dialogic phonograms prepare students for specific language skills. This is a combination of the first two types. In this case, accurate reproduction of the dialogue is not a necessary factor. The main factor is that the student understands the dialogues and imitates what he hears.

Thus, the development of functional literacy in the process of teaching English has the potential to solve the problems of teaching children in various educational institutions. Learning a foreign language can be not only a very educational, but also a complex process. In particular, teaching oral and written speech is a complex process for all categories of children. And most children experience learning difficulties.

Reading in a foreign language is considered one of the most important forms of speech work for most people. Not all of us have the chance to know native speakers (although in the eternity of big technologies this is also not such a gigantic problem), but everyone has every chance to recite. This is why the study of reading acts as a motivated dominant. A reading person is able to think difficultly, grasp the unified and discover the contradictory connections of phenomena, correctly evaluate history and find the right conclusions. Reading creates the properties of a socially valuable person.

Drawing a conclusion, it is possible to state that the active literacy of a student is the task and result of education. Using assignments for the compilation of active literacy, the mentor helps to increase the motivation of students, expands their horizons, develops creative capabilities, and can help comprehend the meanings of the advanced world. Compilation of active

literacy is an essential condition for the work of a teacher. The work must be well thought out, painstakingly planned, carried out systematically, and not “on request”, there must be a possibility of evaluating the results in time. As a result, the child must possess: the joy of successfully interacting with the changing world around him, the ability to solve all kinds of (in what number of non-standard) educational and topical tasks, the ability to build public affairs, a set of reflective skills that provide an assessment of his own literacy, attraction to the upcoming education.

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